

LA-CoNGA physics: an open science education collaboration between Latin America and Europe for High Energy Physics

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Abstract

The communities of astrophysics, astronomers and high energy physicists have been pioneers in establishing Virtual Research and Learning Networks generating international productive consortiums in virtual research environments and forming the new generation of scientists. These environments are key to improve accessibility and inclusion for students and researchers in developing countries and to strengthen the scientific collaboration between developed and developing countries. In this proceeding we will discuss one in particular: LA-CoNGA Physics (Latin American alliance for Capacity building in Advance physics).

LA-CoNGA physics aims to support the modernization of the university infrastructure and the pedagogical offer in advanced physics in four Latin American countries: Colombia, Ecuador, Peru and Venezuela. This virtual teaching and research network is composed of 3 partner universities in Europe and 8 in Latin America, and several academic and industrial partners. The project is co-funded by the European Commission through the Erasmus+ Capacity Building program.

Open science education and open data are at the heart of our operations. In practice LA-CoNGA physics has created a set of postgraduate courses in Advanced Physics (high energy physics and complex systems) that are common and inter-institutional, supported by the installation of interconnected instrumentation laboratories and an open e-learning platform. This program is inserted as a specialization in the Physics masters of the 8 Latin American partners in Colombia, Ecuador, Peru and Venezuela. It is based on three pillars: courses in high energy physics theory/phenomenology, data science and instrumentation. The program is complemented by transversal activities like seminars, citizen science projects and open science hackathons. In the current context, Virtual Research and Learning Networks and e-learning platforms are contributing to solve challenges, such as distance education during the COVID19 pandemic and internationalization of institutions.

1 High Energy, Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics in Latin America: the context

The high energy, cosmology and astroparticle physics (HECAP) community has grown in Latin America in the last decades thanks to the establishment of key experimental facilities in the region (e.g. the Pierre Auger Observatory¹ and The Latin American Giant Observatory²), scientific training mobility programs linking Europe and Latin America (e.g. the High Energy Physics Latin American European Network (HELEN)³ and the European Particle physics Latin America NETWORK (EPLANET)⁴) and Virtual Research and Learning Networks in the region like the Centro Virtual de Altos Estudios en Altas Energías (CEVALE2) [4].

The development of the above mentioned areas in Latin America is nuanced and varies country-by-country. However, it has enormous potential thanks to the diversity of interests/skills and a young generation with potential and eagerness to learn. However, the HECAP community has reached a critical mass and in 2020 the first Latin American Strategy Forum for Research Infrastructure for High Energy, Cosmology and Astroparticle Physics (LASF4RI-HECAP) came to a conclusion, establishing a serie of recommendations and a defining a roadmap for HECAP in the region [5]. LASF4RI-HECAP put in evidence the diversity of interests and skills, the potential and eagerness to learn from the younger generations and the interest in collaborative work within the community.

2 LA-CoNGA physics: what is it?

LA-CoNGA Physics (Latin American alliance for Capacity building in Advance physics) is an European-Latin American network building common capacities in advanced physics training in Latin American universities. This Erasmus+ Capacity Building in Higher Education project co-funded by the European Commission's Education, Audiovisual and Culture Executive Agency brings together 8 universities from Latin America, 3 European universities in France and Germany, and several international and national research centers (including ICTP in Italy, DESY in Germany, CERN in Switzerland as well as CNRS and CEA in France) as well as industrial partners (the Italian instrumentation company CAEN data science start-ups) to contribute to the modernisation, accessibility and internationalisation of higher education in Colombia, Ecuador, Peru and Venezuela.

The LA-CoNGA Physics consortium is composed by the following institutions:

- **Program Partners in Europe:**

- Université Paris Cité (UPC), France (Coordinator)
- Université Paul Sabatier Toulouse, France (UPS)
- Technische Universität Dresden (TUD), Germany

- **Program Partners in Latin America:**

- Colombia: Universidad Antonio Nariño (UAN) and Universidad Industrial de Santander (UIS)
- Ecuador: Universidad San Francisco de Quito (USFQ) and Universidad Yachay Tech

¹PAO: <https://www.auger.org>

²LAGO: <http://lagoproject.net/index.html>

³HELEN: <https://www.roma1.infn.it/exp/helen/>

⁴EPLANET: <https://www.roma1.infn.it/exp/eplanet/>

- Peru: Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería (UNI) and Universidad Nacional Mayor de San Marcos (UNMSM)
- Venezuela: Universidad Central de Venezuela (UCV) and Universidad Simón Bolívar (USB)

• **Associated Partners:**

- International research centers: CERN and ICTP
- National research centers: CNRS and CEA (France), DESY (Germany)
- Industrial partners in Latin America and Europe: CAEN, Frontier X Analytics, DBAccess, E-PISTEME.TECH
- Other academic partners in the Americas: RedCLARA, CEVALE2 (Centro Virtual de Altos Estudios de Altas Energías), New York Academy of Sciences, Asociación Colombiana para el Avance de la Ciencia

A Virtual Research and Learning Network (VRLNs) is a distributed group of researchers working together with large shared instruments through a virtual environment. These scientific environments, based on high-speed networks, distributed computing, video-conferencing and remote instrument operations, are commonly referred to as e-Infrastructures. The European Commission has invested heavily in promoting this type of collaboration among scientists worldwide, funding many international projects to create shared e-Infrastructures around the globe [1, 2, 3]. In this sense LA-CoNGA physics is one of these VRLNs. The project has successfully piloted the creation of a Master’s-level one-year program with key subjects of study Data Science, Instrumentation and Advanced Physics (see Figure 1), as skills highly in demand outside academia. Courses are thought partly remotely from Europe, partly from Latin America, through a dedicated e-learning platform that also provides a Data-Science infrastructure. The installation of modern and interconnected instrumentation laboratories allows students to perform experiments across the universities in the networks. The syllabuses are calibrated on recognized credits and inserted in the Latin American partner’s local Masters programs. Students can follow two different tracks: High Energy Physics (HEP) or Complex Systems (CS).

Figure 1: LA-CoNGA physics syllabus consists of three key subjects of study: Theory, Data Science and Instrumentation. The student’s academic training begins in the first two periods, and the professional/research insertion comes in the last three months with the internships.

3 LA-CoNGA physics: methodology and tools

3.1 Syllabus content and classroom strategy

The *innovative character of the LA-CoNGA physics syllabus is given by:*

- **General:**
 - The courses are divided in mini-modules, which give the flexibility of inviting different experts to cover each minimodule, extending the network. Students from the Latin American partner universities not registered for the full program could follow one or several minimodules if interested.
 - Equal weighting/credits are assigned to the three key subjects. The program gives equal importance to the instrumentation and data science skills developed by the students, as part of an integral training.
 - The one-year Master’s-level program was calibrated following the European Bologna System in terms of number of credits/hours devoted: a full annual load of 60 ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System) credits is required to pass the full program
- **Courses in the first period (12 weeks)**
 - Data Science: emphasis in science reproducibility, good practices in programming and statistics. Exercises based on open-access datasets.
 - Instrumentation: emphasis in learning by doing, with different activities using the remote instrumentation and interconnected laboratories network designed for the two HEP and CS tracks (see also Section 3.3).
 - Theory: a common conceptual field theory framework common to all students, and later split into two different mini-modules or streams: High Energy Physics and Complex Systems. It provides a modern understanding of many cutting-edge phenomena, i.e. spontaneous symmetry breaking and renormalisation group.
- **Courses in the second period (8 weeks):** two courses are mandatory and common to both HEP and CS (“Advanced topics in data science” and “Introduction to Medical Physics”), and one specific to each track (“Astro-particles and Cosmology” for HEP and “Advanced statistical mechanics” for CS)
- **Internships (12 weeks):** students following the full one-year program can have access to research or industrial internships (thanks to the support of our industrial partners). The internship work is structured as follows: an initial pre-internship report to be completed after two weeks of bibliographical review, the internship work, and finally it’s written report with an oral presentation during the LA-CoNGA physics Network School at the end of academic year.

The project officially started in January 2020, with an initial funding approved for 3 years and extended an extra year due to the COVID pandemic. So far, LA-CoNGA physics community is composed by 3 cohorts: 2021, 2022, 2023, including around 30 instructors from Latin America and Europe and more than 50 students has completed at least one full course in each cohort (between 10 and 15 students have completed their internships each year). A mix of synchronous and asynchronous activities were designed for each course, coordinated through the e-learning open-access platform, and complemented with extra academic support including individual mentorships, discussion forums, office hours and discussion sessions. The teaching material is developed in Spanish and to-date more than 200 open access

classes (including videos, documents, notebooks, datasets...) are available in the project website⁵.

3.2 E-learning open-access platform

Our e-learning open-access platform, called MiLAB⁶, was created in collaboration with our partner RedCLARA (for Cooperación Latinoamericana de Redes Avanzadas). MiLAB compiles different tools for project and group management, preservation of digital history and collaborative work. MiLAB integrates different open-access tools: a Git repository for version control of source codes and documents, a data repository to preserve and give access to samples from instrumental measurements and computer-generated data, and also includes an instant messaging tool and a computational interface. The instant messaging system organizes and stores team discussions. The computational interface allows the users to process and analyze data from the repository or directly from an instrument. All codes and generated data, saved into git and/or data repositories, can be shared among users.

3.3 Remote access interconnected instrumentation labs

Instrumentation labs are currently installed in 7 out of the 8 universities in Latin America and they include CAEN educational kits for Nuclear Physics experiments, National Instruments laboratory toolkits, air-quality monitoring stations for high-school science labs and computing stations. First on-site laboratory practices took place in 2022 due to delays in the equipment purchase and installation related to administrative procedures and the COVID pandemic. The 2020 and 2021 student cohorts had difficulties accessing the equipment in their universities. This motivated the development of an innovative platform that enables students to access and operate these instruments remotely, regardless of their geographic location. Four specific laboratory practices are conducted through this platform. Three of them are nuclear physics experiments performed using the instruments from the premium CAEN SP5600 kit (photon spectroscopy, SiPM characterization and cosmic muon detection) and the fourth one is a complex systems experiment using a chaotic double pendulum built entirely from scratch in collaboration with our partner E-PISTEME.TECH. Documentation and management tasks from the laboratory side are needed to guarantee an excellent remote lab experience. Such activities include scheduling the experiments, user authentication, user interfaces and statistics (number of users, location, connection time, results and reports). Currently the team is working in consolidating the training of technical staff for new instrumentation remote labs and is in contact with CAEN and E-PISTEME.TECH to improve the front-end of the remote instrumentation laboratories.

4 LA-CoNGA physics: beyond the courses

Capacity building goes beyond the formal courses created and taught within LA-CoNGA physics. All consortium members have played an important role in implementing the project, with well-defined and different levels of responsibilities and tasks. This ensures they acquire/strengthen the needed skills and know-how about the project and increase their professional networks. Our code of conduct, communication plan, diversity policy and data management plan are crucial ingredients of

⁵LA-CoNGA Physics: <https://laconga.redclara.net>

⁶<https://milab.redclara.net>

our vision and mission. Additional activities have been organised by the consortium, including but not limited to:

- Other academic activities: open-access cycle of seminars taking place usually every two weeks, LA-CoNGA Network School organised at the end of the academic year
- Scientific outreach: workshops about science communication during our network schools and communication strategy through our website and social media
- Transversal to other communities: hackaton LA-CoNGA physics Co-Afina 2022⁷ and citizen science projects with high-schools in the region using air-quality monitoring stations.

5 Conclusions and outlook

During the last 4 years LA-CoNGA physics has contributed to the modernisation and accessibility of the higher education systems in the partner universities but more importantly it has strengthened the cross-institutional relations between European and Latin American partners through the training of the new generations of scientists.

Albeit the challenges faced, which included the COVID pandemic and the inhomogeneity in terms of resources and training in the partner institutions, LA-CoNGA physics initiative has successfully built a dynamic, collaborative, interconnected, and diverse VRLN in advanced physics. The proof of concept has been described in this document. The consortium members are currently working to ensure the sustainability beyond initial funding period and continue contributing to the capacity building, talent pipeline and intraregional and European-Latin American networking. We envision similar experiences in other disciplines in different geographic regions.

References

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⁷<https://laconga.redclara.net/hackathon/2022/>